

The Influence of Product Quality, Promotion and Brand Image on Consumer Satisfaction

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ABSTRACT

Research to determine consumer responses and the influence of product quality, promotion and brand image on consumer satisfaction at The Coffee Legend, both simultaneously and partially. The subjects of this research are consumers who have made purchases, the sample in this research is 100 respondents. This type of research is descriptive and verification. Test the instrument using validity and reliability tests. Data analysis includes multiple regression, determination tests and simultaneous and partial significance tests. The research results show: (1) The average consumer response to consumer satisfaction at The Coffee Legend is the highest product quality, (2) Product quality, promotion and brand image have a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction partially or simultaneously

INTRODUCTION

Coffee production plays a role in the national economy. Obtaining this coffee commodity is sufficient to support Indonesia's national economy. This natural wealth is utilized by business people to open culinary businesses that provide a varied coffee menu. The many types of coffee in Indonesia have made coffee creators innovate in terms of making coffee. In South Oku itself, the coffee phenomenon has encouraged business opportunities from coffee shops, cafes to restaurants.

With the existence of café competitors other than The Coffee Legend, it certainly creates sales competition, each company has certain ways to increase consumer satisfaction. These conditions encourage business people to carry out the right strategies, one of which is paying attention to product quality, promotion and good brand image. The Coffee Legend is one of the well-known coffee companies in South OKU, the coffee offered varies, here is coffee sales data in 2022:

Table 1. Revenue Data for The Coffee Legend in 2022

Month	Revenue Target (RP)	Realization of Income (Rp)	Percentage of Achievement (%)	Information
January	60.000.000	45.000.000	75	Not Achieved
February	60.000.000	48.000.000	85	Not Achieved
March	60.000.000	52.500.000	88	Not Achieved
April	60.000.000	60.200.000	100	Achieved
May	60.000.000	52.000.000	87	Not Achieved
June	60.000.000	54.250.000	90	Not Achieved
July	60.000.000	60.320.000	101	Achieved
August	60.000.000	58.200.000	97	Not Achieved
September	60.000.000	61.000.000	102	Achieved
October	60.000.000	62.000.000	103	Achieved
November	60.000.000	58.000.000	97	Not Achieved
December	60.000.000	61.250.000	102	Achieved
Total	720.000.000	672.720.000	93	Not Achieved
Average	60.000.000	56.060.000	93	Not Achieved

Source: The Coffe Legend (Processed), 2023

Based on Tabel Fabric 1, the target for other coffee sellers reaches IDR 56.060.000, with other sellers reaching 93%. Meanwhile, for other reasons, the company's target is not achieved, to find out whether the company's target is not achieved, a survey is carried out regarding the research title.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The results of the pre-survey and interviews that have been carried out show that there are problems with the product quality variable, namely that the quality of The Coffee Legend products is not appropriate, where consumers' assessment of The Coffee Legend products does not have a distinctive aroma

and the product packaging is still less attractive so it cannot meet consumer expectations.

The promotion variable states that the promotions carried out were less than optimal because the promotional messages conveyed did not attract the attention of consumers enough, the advertisements on social media and the discounts given did not work well, while in the brand image variable the brand image was well known and the coffee beans produced were of sufficient quality.

METHODOLOGI

According to Tjiptono (2017:45) consumer satisfaction is a basic element in modern marketing thinking and practice. Satisfaction indicators consist of Conformity to expectations, interest in visiting again and, willingness to recommend Rendra and Tony (2020) state that the factors that influence consumer satisfaction are product quality, promotion and brand image.

According to Tjiptono (2016:134) Product quality is a characteristic of a product in terms of its capabilities to fulfill needs that have been determined and have a latent nature. Product quality indicators are: Performance, additional features or characteristics, rehabilitation, conformity with specifications, durability, ability to serve, aesthetics, perceived quality. Rendara Maingku et al (2022:127), stated that product quality has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction.

The next factor that influences consumer satisfaction is promotion. According to Kotler and Keller (2016: 154), promotion is an activity that communicates the superiority of a product and persuades consumers to buy that product. Promotion indicators include: Promotional messages, promotional media, promotion time. Gilang Riki (2022:117) states that promotions have a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction.

According to Firmansyah (2019:60), brand image is the perception that appears in the minds of consumers when they remember a brand for a particular product. Brand image indicators include 1) manufacturer's image; 2) user image and; 3) product image. Rendra and Tony (2020:121) state that brand image has a positive and significant influence on consumer satisfaction. The research method used is descriptive and verification with a quantitative approach.

Variable Operations

The variables of this research consist of dependent variables, namely consumer satisfaction (Y) and independent variables, namely product quality (X1), promotion (X2) and brand image (X3).

Population and Sample

The population in this study were consumers of The Coffee Legend with a population of 7005 people. The sample calculation results using Taro Yamane were 98.69 samples rounded up to 100 respondents.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Multiple linear regression analysis to determine whether there is an influence of product quality, promotion and brand image on consumer satisfaction, the function or equation is as follows:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + e$$

Multiple Correlation Analysis

To find out the relationship between product quality, promotion and brand image on consumer satisfaction with The Coffee Legend.

Analysis of the Coefficient of Determination

To find out the percentage change in the dependent variable (Y) caused by the independent variable (X).

Hypothesis test

Hypothesis testing is carried out using the F test and t test

1. Simultaneous Hypothesis Testing

- a. If $F_{count} \leq F_{table}$ at $\alpha = 0.05$ then H_0 is accepted and H_a is rejected, meaning that product quality, promotion and brand image do not have a joint influence on consumer satisfaction.
- b. If $F_{count} > F_{table}$ at $\alpha = 0.05$ then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, meaning that product quality, promotion and brand image have a joint influence on consumer satisfaction.

2. Partial Hypothesis Testing

- a. For product quality, promotion or brand image, if t_{count} is smaller or equal to t_{table} ($t_{count} \leq t_{table}$) at $\alpha = 0.05$ then H_0 is accepted and H_a is rejected, meaning that each of the product quality, promotion and brand image does not have a positive and significant influence on consumer satisfaction.
- b. Meanwhile, if t_{count} is greater than t_{table} ($t_{count} > t_{table}$) at $\alpha = 0.05$ then H_a is accepted, meaning that each product quality, promotion or brand image has a positive and significant influence on consumer satisfaction.

Table 2. Summary of Consumer Characteristics

No	Karakteristik	Ciri-ciri konsumen	Persentase (%)
1	Jenis Kelamin	Laki-Laki	62
2	Usia	26-35	55
3	Pendidikan	SMA	51
4	Profesi	Pegawai Swasta	30
5	Penghasilan	Rp.3,1-Rp.5 Jt	26

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2023

Based on Table 2, it can be concluded that more men visit The Coffee Legend at 62%, while the after category is dominated by teenagers aged 26-35 years at 55%. The level of consumer education is dominated by high school graduates at 51% with jobs dominated by private sector employees at 30% and incomes in the range of Rp. 3,100,000 to Rp. 5,000,000 by 26%.

The results of processing the questionnaire are consumer responses to determine the influence of product quality, promotion and brand image on consumer satisfaction. The respondents' responses are as follows:

Respondents' Responses to Product Quality

The following are the results of analysis of consumer responses regarding variable indicators of product quality:

Table 3. Recapitulation of Respondents' Responses to Product Quality Variables

No	Description	Value	Categori	Interpretation
1				
Performance				
a	Coffee products from The Coffee Legend have a very delicious reputation	3,63	Good	As consumers choose The Coffee Legend, the coffee presented in Taiwairkain has a unique reputation for its delicious coffee presentation.
b	Coffee products from The Coffee Legend can be enjoyed in various situations	3,69	Good	As consumers choose The Coffee Legend, the coffee in Taiwairkain can be enjoyed in various situations, making it suitable for tasting pain and rain.
2				
Featurs (Fitur atau Ciri-ciri)				
a	Coffee products from The Coffee Legend have a unique aroma when brewed	3,39	Petty Good	As consumers choose The Coffee Legend, the coffee in Taiwairkain has a unique aroma when brewed, but the aroma does not last well.
b	Coffee products from The Coffee Legend have distinctive coffee flavors	3,43	Good	As consumers choose The Coffee Legend, Kairenai Coffee in Taiwairkain has unique coffee characteristics and is enjoyed for example, payday sweet taste which is soft strong taste and sharp
3				
Reability				
a	Products from The Coffee Legend contain nutrients that are good for the body.	3,5	Good	Consumers choose The Coffee Legend because the coffee in Taiwairkain contains nutrients that are good for the body, such as vitamins B2, B3 and B5.
b	Products from The Coffee Legend are quality with selected coffee beans.	3,54	Good	Consumers choose The Coffee Legend because of its products which are made from high-quality fabrics with self-stained coffee beans
4				
Conferrance to spesification				
a	The Coffee Legend products conform to the quality we guarantee.	3,62	Good	As consumers choose The Coffee Legend, Kairenai has quality which is guaranteed to be like Raisai which is delicious.
b	The Coffee Legend products are delicious to enjoy	3,56	Good	As consumers choose The Coffee Legend because the products in Taiwairkain have a certificate of quality to be enjoyed so consumers are not afraid to try them.
5				
Durability				
a	Raisai Kopi The Coffee Legend is still delicious even though it is cold	3,88	Good	Even though consumers choose The Coffee Legend, the Coffee Legend coffee is still delicious to enjoy even when it is cold, for example, the payday coffee variation latte is not always easy to enjoy.
b	The Coffee Legend paid packaging coffee product has a long expiration date	3,76	Good	As consumers choose The Coffee Legend, the coffee products in Taiwairkain have a long shelf life so they are suitable for souvenirs.
6				
Serviceability				
a	The Coffee Legend staff provides excellent service	3,62	Good	As consumers choose The Coffee Legend, the staff of The Coffee Legend has provided good services such as providing recommendations for favorite drinks.

Source: Primary data processed, 2023

The recapitulation results stated that respondents' responses to product quality had an average assessment value of 3.54 in the good category. The highest value is the durability indicator of 3.88 in the good category. Meanwhile, the lowest score for the aesthetic indicator was 3.20 in the quite good category.

Respondents' Responses to Promotions

The following are the results of an analysis of consumer pain regarding promotional variable indicators:

Table 4. Recapitulation of Respondents' Responses to Promotion Variables

No	Description	Value	Categori	Interprestasion
1				
Pesan Promosi				
a	Competitors The promotional information presented by The Coffee Legend is very attractive	3,32	Pretty Good	As consumers choose The Coffee Legend, the promotional information offered is quite attractive, such as Vailentine's paid hair, available on a buy 1 get 1 basis, but the promotion is offered specifically for the first 2 buyers.
b	Promotions are packaged using Baihaisai which is easy to understand	3,33	Pretty Good	While consumers choose The Coffee Legend because the promotions that are implemented are quite popular with consumers, the Baihaisai that is used is also very good.
2				
Promotion media				
a	Anda mendapatkan iklan The Coffe Legend melalui melalui media cetak dan elektronik	3,51	Good	As consumers choose The Coffee Legend, the advertisements carried out by The Coffee Legend via electronic print media are accepted by consumers who are paid for Instagram stories paid for Instagram
b	Media promotions carried out by The Coffee Legend can be accepted by all consumers	3,56	Good	As consumers choose The Coffee Legend, the promotional media carried out by The Coffee Legend are easily targeted by consumers who use social media and Instagram.
3				
Promotion media				
a	Time to know that promotions will take place at the most competitive times	3,36	Pretty Good	As consumers choose The Coffee Legend, the duration of the promotion carried out by The Coffee Legend is quite appropriate for the time and moment of interest, but the duration of the experience is too short.
b	The Coffee Legend provides discounts with different types of time	3,33	Pretty Good	Consumers choose The Coffee Legend because of the discounts that are provided quite well with the terms and conditions that are clear according to consumers, the terms and conditions which are determined are related to the terms and conditions which are accelerated.
Total		20,41		Consumer assessment of promotions has an average value of 3.40 in the quite good category, but there are several things that companies must pay attention to, such as promotional media.
Average		3,40	Pretty Good	

Source: Primary data processed, 2023

The results of the results showed that respondents regarding the promotion had a score of 3.40 with quite a good performance. The highest indicator is media promotion with a value of 3.56, including good performance. The lowest score is the lowest indicator for promotional competitors with a value of 3.32.

Respondents' Responses to Brand Image

The following are the results of consumer analysis regarding the variable indicators of brand image:

Table 5. Recapitulation of Respondents' Responses Regarding Brand Image Variables

No	Description	Value	Category	Interprestasion
1			Citra Pembuat	
a	The Coffee Legend is a trusted coffee company	3,39	Pretty Good	As consumers choose The Coffee Legend, the brand's coffee products are already good enough to be one of the most trusted coffee companies in terms of quality coffee beans, but in terms of delivery, delays often occur.
b	The Coffee Legend is a coffee shop company that is easily known.	3,52	Good	As consumers choose The Coffee Legend, Kairenai has become a coffee shop company that is easy to get to know and doesn't taste good either. .
2			User image	
a	Consuming coffee at The Coffee Legend improves the fabric of life for this beautiful life	3,45	Good	As consumers choose The Coffee Legend, they can be consumed to enjoy the life of the world, this is like a coffee trend with various flavors so it is loved by various people.
b	Aid your satisfaction in enjoying The Coffee Legend products	3,59	Good	As consumers choose The Coffee Legend, consumers have their satisfaction when it comes to enjoying coffee from The Coffee Legend, such as the presentation of the products that consumers have achieved.
3			User Image	
a	The Coffee Legend products are made from special coffee beans	3,57	Good	Consumers choose The Coffee Legend because the product it sells is a special coffee bean that is produced in-house by another company which makes it different from other coffees.
b	The Coffee Legend has quality coffee products	3,45	Good	Consumers choose The Coffee Legend because the products in Taiwan have good quality from selected coffee beans.
	Total	20,97		Consumer assessment of brand image has an average value of 3.49 in the good category
	Average	3,495	Good	

Source: Primary data processed, 2023

The results of the review show that respondents regarding brand image have a rating of 3.49 with good performance. The highest value indicator is Citrai'' at 3.59 with a good correlation. The lowest indicator, namely image level, is 3.39, which is quite good.

Respondents' Responses to Consumer Satisfaction

The following are the results of a survey of respondents regarding variable indicators of consumer satisfaction:

Table 6. Recapitulation of Respondents' Responses to Consumer Satisfaction Variables

No	Description	Value	Category	Interprestasion
1				
Conformity to Expectations				
a	The promotional information message conveyed by The Coffee Legend is very interesting	3,28	High enough	Some consumers choose The Coffee Legend because the products offered by The Coffee Legend are quite in line with what consumers expect, but the aroma of the coffee does not last long.
b	Promotions are packaged using language that is easy to understand	3,48	High	Some consumers choose The Coffee Legend because they think the service provided by The Coffee Legend is in line with consumer expectations, such as smiles, greetings and greetings.
2				
Interested in Visiting Again				
a	I will come back to buy drinks at The Coffee Legend	3,47	High	Consumers choose The Coffee Legend because of its high product quality and attracting consumer attention for repeat visits.
b	I will definitely make The Coffee Legend my main choice	3,21	High Enough	As consumers choose The Coffee Legend, the quality of the products offered by The Coffee Legend is already quite high, but has not yet become a top choice.
3				
Willingness to Recommend				
a	I recommend The Coffee Legend to my friends.	3,55	High	As consumers choose The Coffee Legend because of the products offered, The Coffee Legend has its satisfaction when visiting, so consumers are willing to recommend other products, the satisfaction is found in the example of the quality of the coffee.
b	I also say positive results about The Coffee Legend	3,35	High Enough	As consumers choose The Coffee Legend because of the positive reviews that consumers have received, it has become a topic of conversation with their friends about The Coffee Legend products, but the popularity of the coffee is almost the same as in general.
Total		20,34		
Average		3,39	High Enough	Consumer assessments regarding customer satisfaction have an average value of 3.39 in the quite high category, but some things must be improved by the company in terms of indicators of conformity to expectations.

Source: Primary data processed, 2023

The results of the results showed that respondents in terms of consumer satisfaction had a score of 3.39 with quite high levels of correlation. The indicator with the highest value is the willingness to recommend as much as 3.55 with a high level of interest, while the score with the lowest value is the willingness to pay for the visit interest indicator of 3.25 with a fairly high level of value.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

This also results in calculations to see the influence of product quality, promotion and brand image simultaneously on consumer satisfaction, the results can be seen in the results of linear regression tests using simultaneous results.

Table 7. Multiple Linear Regression

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1(Constant)	3,287	2,324		2,452	,153
PRODUCT QUALITY (X1)	,141	,042	,241	2,272	,002
PROMOTION(X2)	,115	,063	,203	2,404	,003
BRAND-IMAGE (X3)	,347	,069	,575	4,973	,000

a. Dependent Variable: CONSUMER_SATISFACTION (Y)

Source: Primary data processed, 2023

Based on the results of the calculations of Table 7, it can be concluded that the regression competition is as follows:

$$Y = 3,287 + 0,141 X1 + 0,115 X2 + 0,347 X3 + \varepsilon$$

These results are interpreted as follows:

1. The product quality regression coefficient (X1) = 0.141 has a positive value, which means that if there is an increase in the variable quality of the product, the increase in product quality is followed by an increase in consumer satisfaction with other variable assumptions but.
2. The promotion regression coefficient (X2) = 0.115 has a positive value, which means that if there is an increase in promotional variables, the results are followed by an increase in consumer satisfaction with other variable assumptions, however.
3. Brand image regression coefficient (X3) = 0.347 has a positive value, which means that there is an increase in brand image variable value, the value is followed by an increase in consumer satisfaction with other variable assumptions but still.

Correlation Coefficient Analysis

The main influence is independent variable product quality, promotion and brand image which are variables dependent on consumer satisfaction with The Coffee Legend Bogor simultaneously and can be seen from the following brands:

Table 8. Results of Multiple Correlation Analysis

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,735 ^a	,550	,525	3,191

a. Predictors: (Constant), BRAND_IMAGE, PRODUCT_QUALITY, PROMOTION
b. Dependent Variable: CUSTOMER_SATISFACTION

Source: Primary data processed, 2023

Based on Table 8, the R value is 0.734, meaning the relationship between product quality, promotion and brand image on consumer satisfaction is strong.
Analysis of the Coefficient of Determination

The obtained R Square value is 0.550 or 55%. This result shows that the percentage contribution to the overall independent variable is 55%. The remaining 45% is influenced by other factors that are not included in this

research area such as service quality, location, employee service, facility, and view data (Tjiptono, and Gregorius 2016:295).

Hypothesis Results

1. F-Test

To test the statistical hypothesis above, the F test statistic obtained through the Analysis of Variations (Anova) table is used as shown in the table below:

Table 9. F Test Results

ANOVA ^a					
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F Sig.
1	Regression	1145.231	3	381.744	37.499 .000 ^b
	Residual	977.279	96	10.180	
	Total	2122.510	99		

a. Dependent Variable: CONSUMER SATISFACTION
 b. Predictors: (Constant), BRAND IMAGE, PRODUCT QUALITY, PROMOTION

Source: Primary data processed, 2023

Based on the F value in Table 8, Fcount is 37,499 and the F_{table} value for α = 0.05, which shows that F_{count} is greater than F_{table} (37,499 > 3.290) and the probability value is smaller than the standard probability value (0.000 < 0.05). Thus, it can be concluded that H0 is rejected and Ha is accepted, meaning that with a 95% confidence level the independent variables, namely product quality (X1), promotion (X2) and brand image (X3), have a positive and significant effect together (simultaneously) on Consumer satisfaction (Y).

2. T-test

To see the variables product quality (X1) promotion (X2), brand image (X3) on consumer satisfaction (Y), it can be seen in the partial regression test.

Table 10. T-test results

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3,287	2,324		2,452	,153
	PRODUCT_QUALITY(X1)	,141	,042	,241	2,272	,002
	PROMOTION(X2)	,115	,063	,203	2,404	,003
	BRAND_IMAGE (X3)	,347	,069	,575	4,973	,000

a. Dependent Variable: CUSTOMER_SATISFACTION(Y)

Source: Primary data processed, 2023

Based on Table 10, you can see the t_{count} value and significant value of each independent variable. Meanwhile, the t_{table} value for α = 0.05 is 1.290, so:

- a. Quality Product with a t_{count} of 2,272 is greater than t_{table} (2,272 > 1.290) and a significant value (0.002 < 0.05). Thus, partially Product Quality has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction.

- b. Promotion with a t_{count} of 2,404 is greater than t_{table} ($2,404 > 1.290$) and has a significant value ($0.003 < 0.05$). Thus, promotion partially has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction.
- c. Brand image with t_{count} of 4,973 is greater than t_{table} ($4,973 > 1.290$) and has a significant value ($0.000 < 0.05$). Thus, partially brand image has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction.

CONCLUSSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Consumer responses regarding product quality are in good criteria. The statement item with the highest score is an indicator of durability in the good category. Meanwhile, the lowest score for the aesthetic indicator is in the quite good category. Consumers experience promotions with fairly good criteria. The highest score item is an indicator of promotion media with good links as well and the lowest score, namely a promotional competitor indicator with good links. Consumers are aware of the brand image with good criteria. The item with the highest score is the product image indicator with good quality. The lowest indicator is the manufacturer's image with good quality. The result of consumer satisfaction is that the customer satisfaction criteria are quite high, the item has the highest value score in terms of willingness to recommend indicators with high levels of satisfaction, as the score with the lowest value in terms of interest in visiting the site is quite high. Product quality, promotion and brand image simultaneously (simultaneously) have a positive and significant influence on consumer satisfaction with The Coffee Legend. In combination with each product quality variable, promotion and brand image have a positive and significant influence on consumer satisfaction.

Product quality has an impact on consumer satisfaction, The Coffee Legend has carried out improvements to improve product quality and quality, as well as other indicators that can be assessed and improved product quality at The Co. of Legend is getting better than before. Promotions have an impact on consumer satisfaction and the company must evaluate competitors' promotions that will influence consumers' interest in purchasing The Coffee Legend coffee products. As well as other indicators, it is best to monitor and increase the level of promotion in The Coffee Legend, which is better than before.

To increase consumer satisfaction with brand image variables, the hair company must evaluate and improve the manufacturer's image, such as paying for the product design and quality of the product according to the consumer's expectations, for other indicators it is best to monitor the product and improve the quality of the product again. Or image brand yang aide payday The Coffee Legend is increasing better than before. To become the company's main choice, it requires competitive evaluation by looking at product quality, promotion and brand image with other companies. For other indicators, it is best to ensure that

the quality of the product increases and the quality of consumer satisfaction increases, the higher the value of the product.

FURTHER RESEARCH

Other research is also interested in examining similar aspects, namely product quality, promotion, brand image and consumer satisfaction. To improve the period of research, it is also necessary to carry out similar research that uncovers other factors such as 45% of consumer satisfaction being influenced by the quality variables of hairdressing, hairdressing, etc.

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